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Insights into Wisteria vein mosaic virus: an evolutionary framework for understanding the emergence of new viral threats

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Wisteria vein mosaic virus (WVMV, *Potyvirus wisteriae*), a member of the *Potyvirus* genus, is the causative agent of Wisteria vein mosaic disease (WMD), a severe infection threatening wisteria plants, ornamentals highly valued worldwide. Likely originating in East Asia, WVMV was first officially documented in the United States, and subsequently reported in multiple countries. In Italy, the virus was first identified as the WVMV Bari isolate, and its complete genome was sequenced using NGS barcoding technology. Phylogenetic analysis via PhyML, corroborated by clustering algorithms, revealed a distinct division into two phylogenetic groups. The dominant clade included isolates from *Wisteria* spp., while the minor clade comprised three genetically divergent strains, with sequence identity close to the species boundary, infecting herbaceous non-wisteria hosts. Molecular clock estimates, based on the Relative Time Dated Tips (RTDT) approach, placed the divergence of these lineages around the 17th century. Network inference further validated the genetic separation between the two host-related groups and indicated the potential existence of intermediate variants occurring in the host jump transition. Population genetic analyses demonstrated a pronounced genetic divergence, reinforced by significant permutation tests. The fixation index (F_{ST}) and migrant number (Nm) indicators pointed to limited gene flow and well-structured populations. Negative neutrality tests and a low dN/dS ratio suggested that purifying selection is actively removing deleterious mutations. This study proposes an evolution-based framework approach, using the intriguing evolutionary dynamics of WVMV as a case study to explore how other overlooked potyviruses or newly emerging viruses could spread and infect economically important crops.

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